

LIBRARIANS AS AGENTS OF CHANGE

OPEN EDUCATION
STRATEGY
2024-2026

European Network
of Open Education
Librarians

The vision

Building on the Open Access and Open Science Agenda, European libraries in Higher Education are key, active and trusted partners in achieving Open Education (OE) by making educational resources, services and practices accessible, open and reusable helping make it standard practice.

Mission

Our mission is to support Europe's Higher Education policymakers, librarians, ambassadors and facilitators of OE to help implement the UNESCO OER Recommendation through a targeted and action-oriented approach. We seek to enable the conditions, foster and catalyse the opportunities presented by Open Access and Open Science to maximise the access to, creation, reuse and adaptation of Open Educational Resources (OER), Practices (OEP), services and infrastructure for all and seek to sustain those. We do this whilst respecting and favouring diversity, equity and inclusion (DEI) to reflect and meet local needs.

Target audience

- Primary: European Higher Education (HE) librarians and educational policymakers
- Secondary: other ambassadors and facilitators of OE (professional library associations, faculty members, researchers, instructional designers and practitioners)

5 key goals

1. **Support OE policy development and encourage investment** in OE in Europe's academic institutions for its sustainability.
2. **Raise awareness of the value** of OE, OER and OEP **and stimulate action**, including certain practices such as open textbooks as an essential and effective pedagogical tool.
3. **Advocate for the recognition and reward of OE** people and practices.
4. **Build capacity and upskill librarians** to become even more effective in supporting their teaching staff and students in OE.
5. **Facilitate DEI-rich OEP** across all corners of Europe.

Objectives

1. Support OE policy development and encourage investment in OE in Europe's academic institutions for its sustainability.

- Advocate for the Open Agenda, making clear connections between Open Science policy and Open Education at HE institutions.
- Advocate for the value of OE with institutional policymakers and representatives of international and umbrella organisations that serve Research Performing Organisations (RPOs).
- Provide guidance on OE-related policymaking to all corners of Europe.
- Advocate for investment in OE staff, service and infrastructure development, and other support.

2. Raise awareness of the value of OE, OER and OEP and **stimulate action**, including certain practices such as open textbooks as an essential and effective pedagogical tool.

- Increase awareness of the benefits of OE, OER and OEP amongst educators, librarians and students.
- Stimulate and facilitate institutions to showcase their good practices locally, regionally and internationally, encouraging them to engage with a wide range of stakeholders.
- Gain a better understanding of the OE textbook and promote it as an essential and effective tool for open pedagogies and practices comparable to commercially published textbooks.

3. Advocate for the recognition and reward of OE people and practices.

- Bring the need for recognition and reward of OE efforts into the conversation at decision-making tables.
- Showcase good practices of how OE is being rewarded in Europe and beyond.

4. Build capacity and upskill librarians to become even more effective in supporting their teaching staff and students in OE.

- Provide tools and resources to help upskill the OE librarian in a range of OER-related competencies¹ to effectively address digital transformation developments and taking into account new business models.
- Coach and train librarians in OE practices through interactive events by showcasing good practices developed in European institutions and the open tools they use to support their activities.

5. Facilitate DEI-rich Open Practices across all corners of Europe.

6. Provide guidance on the creation of DEI-sensitive materials through training and resources to serve a wide range of communities and geographically distributed minorities.

¹ UNESCO, (2016), *Open Educational Resources Competency Framework OER*, https://unesdoc.unesco.org/ark:/48223/pf0000266159_eng